

The Mediating Effects of Meta Cognitive Awareness on the Relationship between Professional Commitment on Job Satisfaction

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Abstract:- This study determined the mediating effects of meta cognitive awareness on the relationship between professional commitment on job satisfaction. The quantitative approach using the correlational technique and analysis were utilized in this study with a sample of 300 teachers coming from the Public Elementary Schools of Manay Central District, Division of Davao Oriental using purposive sampling technique. Sets of adapted survey questionnaires were used in obtaining data from the respondents which were subjected for content validity and reliability analysis. The data were analysed using the Mean, Pearson-r, and Multiple Regression Analysis. The results revealed that the levels of of professional commitment was rated high, job satisfaction was also rated as high. While metacognitive awareness was also rated high. Moreover, a significant relationship existed between these variables. A significant relationship between professional commitment and meta cognitive awareness was significant. A significant relationship between meta cognitive awareness and job satisfaction was also significant. A significant relationship between professional commitment and job satisfaction was also significant. The extent of influence of predictor variables on job satisfaction was proven in the study.

Keywords:- educational management, professional commitment, meta cognitive awareness, job satisfaction, Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

If teachers are dissatisfied with their work lives, they will suffer, but their students will suffer as well. Beyond salary, strong work ethics can influence human beings to commit or not to commit a crime. Empowerment within the organization remains weak due to a lack of work ethics that can no longer enhance teachers' job satisfaction. Negative consequences associated with low job satisfaction include lack of active participation in decision-making and often facing ethical issues stemming from teacher's behavior (Steinheider, 2016).

The teacher is the most important factor in the teaching-learning process. The teacher sets the tone and light of the classroom. He is the authority figure providing the direction for behavior. He is a model and is consciously imitated. Thus, good teachers are essential for the effective functioning of the education system and improving the quality of learning. Job satisfaction enables

teachers to put their best to do the assigned work. Maintaining high satisfaction and morale has long been an important objective for educators (Rico & Ertmer, 2015).

Professional commitment is predicted to be a potential mediator in the connection between job satisfaction and organizational commitment, in which the initial job satisfaction of an individual contributes to their professional commitment before finally leading to metacognitive awareness (Stadler et al., 2016; Ritz et al., 2013) and are only experiencing amounts of burnout (Croom, 2003). Chaney (2017) found that beginning teachers who had already left the profession were generally satisfied with their work as teachers but were dissatisfied with their workload and time demands. Walker et al. (2014) found teachers who left the teaching profession were as satisfied as those who remained, but those who left cited family issues as a primary reason for leaving. In addition, the determination of cognitive awareness of teachers concerning their majors and the teaching profession can help them analyze themselves better in a professional manner and may affect their job satisfaction (Northouse, 2010).

With the vision of what motivates operatives, school heads can larger ascertain what makes the teachers do their best job. Managers need to understand what propels their subordinates and colleagues to be competent heads in the workplace. The recommendations in this study will enable school heads to become the best presentation out of their operatives and raise productivity in their departments. Further, the influence of the commitment on job satisfaction has been studied extensively but not on metacognitive awareness. In the above context, the researcher took an interest in examining if the metacognitive awareness mediates the relationship between professional commitment and teachers' job satisfaction; hence, making this study a generation of new knowledge that can give a specific contribution to the field of education.

Further, this study aims to find out the relationship between the mediating effects of metacognitive awareness on the relationship between professional commitment and job satisfaction.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

A. Professional Commitment

Committed teachers tend to perform the roles effectively that their job requires and establish a good teacher-student relationship following professional values. This approach facilitates student learning and the development of terminal behaviors. However, in the clash of the career goals and values and the goals and values of the school, the importance of dedication and commitment increases (Hansen, 2017).

The concept of professional commitment signifies an attitude reflecting the strength of the bond between an employee and an organization. Most of the authors define this concept as the strength of an individual's identification with and involvement in an organization or the psychological attachment felt by an individual within an organization and reflecting the degree to which an individual has interiorized and adopted the organization's characteristics or perspective (Ghosh, 2016).

The first indicator is affective professional commitment. Affective commitment can be characterized as the emotional connection between the employee and the organization. It can be defined as the identification and emotional commitment of the employee towards the organization, leading to them remaining there (Cho & Huang, 2012; Meyer, 2014). Affective commitment is developed through previous work experiences in the organization, which usually satisfy employees' psychological needs (e.g., the development of competencies) and thus makes them feel comfortable within the organization and competent when performing their job (Topolnytsky, 1998; Ng, 2015).

Affective commitment has been considered a commitment based on the individual's identification with and involvement. It is an emotional commitment, where school heads that are a great deal affectively connected to an organization stay within it because they want to (Ozutku, 2018). The quality of teaching depends a great deal on the level of teachers' involvement concerning the profession exerted, the organization one is part of, and the professional satisfaction that one feels. On the one side, the relationship with teacher establishes with one's students, the nature of the teaching activity and the work carried on in the professional community, and the relations with peers, superiors, and students' parents lead to professional achievement and, indirectly, it reflects into the achievements of one's students (McCready et al., 2010).

Meanwhile, affective commitment refers to the strong belief and acceptance of goals and professional values and the will to make considerable efforts to fulfill the professional objectives and responsibilities. Along with their professional experience, school heads effectively involve themselves in their activity, establishing effective relationships with peers and students. The studies proved that the empathy and ability to transpose oneself in another person's situation as if you were the other such as teacher's professional trait, develops and strengthens in time and has a strong affective component. Other studies on the

teacher's affective abilities confirm they develop in time, along with performing the teaching profession, and they turn into steady personality traits (McMahon et al., 2013).

Professional commitment is recognized as a natural ingredient of the teaching profession. It is closely connected to school heads' work performance, absenteeism, burnout, and turnover and has an important influence on students' achievement and attitude towards school. Often, teachers come to be in the profession because of their pull toward the students. They feel a devotion to educating, and therefore their priority as a teacher is to their students and their learning. Committed teachers always put their students' wants, needs, and interests first. They strive to motivate and engage students, and they understand that not every child will learn in the same way (Demir, 2015).

Teachers occupy a pivotal place of importance in the education system. Indeed, no one is more responsible for taking a country forward in the race of modernization and, at the same time, imparting character to the personalities of the young than the teachers. All planning, buildings, equipment, instructional material, organization, etc., could fail if the right type of teachers is missing (Day et al., 2007). In addition, affective commitment has been considered a commitment based on the individual's identification with and involvement in the organization. It is an emotional commitment, where people that are a great deal affectively connected to an organization stay within it because they want to (Delima, 2015).

The second indicator is the continuance of professional commitment. This involves appraisals of personal investments tied to one's current employment and the availability of employment alternatives (Meyer & Allen, 1991). Employees with strong continuance commitment maintain their employment relationship because it provides desirable personal outcomes that they are unwilling to forego or perceive a lack of employment opportunities elsewhere (Riveros & Tsai, 2011, Cho & Huang, 2012).

School heads were more likely to persist in the profession and the same building when they were involved in constant learning and development. The more also they stay if they are informed, included in common decision making, frequently renewed, and motivated through cooperative determinations (Brown & Wynn, 2009; Tait, 2018).

Continuance commitment means that the workers cannot risk quitting their jobs as they realize the cost of giving up the opportunities such as wages, pension rights, and profit-sharing. The workers keep working at the present organization as there are no alternative job opportunities, and they will experience difficulties transferring their basic skills to another organization constitutes continuance commitment. Such commitment is also called rational commitment, which means continuing to be a member of that organization as leaving would cost high. Moreover, throughout the study, teachers are more committed to the organization when they are delivered

sufficient funds and provisions from the administrators (Brown & Wynn, 2009; Steers, 2009).

Moreover, this conveys that the school heads are persistently staying in an organization because of personal investment, retirement benefits, and faculty development offered by the government. Consequently, it makes school heads feel that: staying in an organization is a matter of necessity as much as they desire; very hard for them to leave their organization even if they wanted to; much of their lives will be disrupted if they decide they want to leave their organization; they have too few options to consider leaving their organization; have the willingness to remain on their organization because of personal investment in non-transferable investment; and continue staying in their organization because of their close working relationship with co-workers (Tweve, 2015).

Further, continuance commitment means that the workers cannot risk quitting their jobs as they realize the cost of giving up the opportunities such as wages, pension rights, and profit-sharing. The workers keep working at the present organization as there are no alternative job opportunities, and they will experience difficulties transferring their basic skills to another organization constitutes continuance commitment (Ozutku, 2018).

In the same vein, such commitment is also called rational commitment, which means continuing to be a member of that organization as leaving would cost high. Moreover, Dependable throughout the study is that teachers are more committed to the organization when they are delivered sufficient funds and provisions from the administrators. School heads were more likely to persist in the profession and the same building when they were involved in constant learning and development. The more also they stay if they are informed, included in common decision making, frequently renewed, and motivated through cooperative determinations (Brown & Wynn, 2009; Denton, 2019).

The third indicator is normative professional commitment. This expresses that the school heads are obligated to remain in the organization due to believing that it is moral and right. Also, this implies that teachers feel that: they are guilty if they leave their organization now; their organization deserves their loyalty; they owe a great deal to their organization; they have loyalty to their organization because of family investment in the organization; and they have to stay in their organization because they still have to contribute to the effectiveness of their organization (Kardes, 2009; Shashi, 2014).

In addition, normative commitment is based upon an ideology or a sense of obligation towards the organization, on the individual's moral belief that it is right and moral to continue within the organization. People with a high normative commitment stay within an organization because they think they should. This feeling of obligation results from internalizing the norms exerted on the individual before following his admission into the organization

through a process of familial or cultural socialization and, accordingly, organizational socialization (Kardeş, 2019).

The introductory presentation and discussion of various literature helped highlight the importance of the influence of professional commitment on their teaching competence. These served as support to the results and findings of the study.

B. Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is an important concept that is not only related to an individual, but it is relevant to society's wellbeing. Job satisfaction is one factor that will ensure class performance and productivity of schools. The teachers would get interested in teaching their students effectively when satisfied with their jobs. Like India, other countries are trying to improve their quality of education to meet Teachers who would perform to maximum capacity only if they are satisfied with their jobs. So, job satisfaction is an important phenomenon in every sector, especially in the teaching profession (Chen, 2010).

If the teachers work under stress, they cannot be satisfied, negatively impacting the job. So, it is necessary to identify the factors that influence the teachers to derive satisfaction from their work. Teachers can do wonders for transforming the students' raw materials into excellent finished goods, that is, as complete human beings and responsible citizens. Additional energy can be developed when the teachers are satisfied with their job (Rehman, 2015).

Meanwhile, the role of teachers in society and education can change, but the importance of their position remains the same. Attracting and retaining quality teachers is a great challenge to educational institutions. In education, the essential quality of the teacher is to have a positive approach. Every teacher must have the potential and clear intention to discharge their duty with utmost devotion to derive satisfaction from their work. Job satisfaction is the combination of emotional and psychological experience at any work. Job Satisfaction is the relationship between what everyone expects according to what everyone achieves. Any work cannot be effectively done without satisfaction (Ghosh, 2015).

The first domain is security. Teachers' job satisfaction is the sense of fulfillment and pride felt by people who enjoy their work and do it well. Job satisfaction is also how a job provides gratification, actualization, and enjoyment to the worker. Job satisfaction is also used to refer to the degree to which a teacher is happy with their success in meeting their career goals and expectation (Oh et al., 2017).

Moreover, job dissatisfaction, on the other hand, occurs when an individual is not happy with their job at the workplace and therefore cannot be relied upon to give full devotion to the job assigned. That dissatisfaction occurs when an individual fails to achieve the desired goal. Indeed, there are possible reactions to dissatisfaction. These can be summarized under four broad headings:

aggression, regretfulness, fixation, and withdrawal (Khuong& Vu, 2014).

The many and varied problems tend to reduce the morale of teachers to deliver in their various classrooms. Offices of the teacher's employer – The Ghana Education Services (GES) and the Ghana National Association of Teachers (GNAT), are inundated with calls from furious teachers seeking answers to problems related to their salaries (Govaerts, Kyndt, Dochy, & Baert, 2011).

Moreover, the pay problems facing some teachers across the country have dampened their spirits, and its concomitant negative effect on the work output cannot be ignored. While GNAT will continue to contact the appropriate Ministries and Departments to seek solutions to the legitimate concerns of these affected teachers under its umbrella, we hope that due diligence will be done by the new government so that teachers will be encouraged to contribute their full quota to the development of our dear country (Loganathan, & Dharmaraj, 2017).

The second domain is on work environment. The work environment directly impacts the employees' job satisfaction with the construction industry regarding the managers. Most managers perceive remuneration, job security, working hours, and information in time as important to get effective results. It was revealed that there is a strong relationship between job characteristics, working conditions with job satisfaction, such as job grade, dirt, and humidity, noise, lighting, sufficient space for work, cooperation with others to solve problems, observing rules and procedures, and to abide with duties. These factors directly impact organizational performance (Kavita, 2016).

Due to this, working environmental factors such as pay, decision-making authority, promotional policies, enjoyable co-workers and advancement, job security, support from superior and reward systems, etc., are the main sources to enhance job satisfaction and morale of the employees. It was found that there is a strong relationship between working environment and stress (Jamal, 2018)

The third domain is job responsibilities. Strong work ethics in the organization is the key to the ethical behavior of employees. Organizations that focus on developing strong work ethics relevant to the issues faced by employees will lead to the employees behaving ethically (Valentine & Barnett, 2013). Hence, the organization always looks for employees who can perform their job well. Employees with strong work ethics are reliable, hardworking, and use great efforts. There appear to be four broad categories of theory about work ethics and more specific and concrete theories on satisfaction (Alsop & Heinsohn, 2015; Apasu, 2011).

The degree to which teachers are guided by their moral beliefs is considered independent. Teachers have the right to be guided by their interests in the organization. Each teacher in the organization confirms what is right and wrong. The dimensions associated with independence with the principle of ethics are related to the teachers' personal

and moral beliefs. Employees focus on themselves and are guided by their ethics (Islam et al., 2018).

The fourth domain is community attachments/linkages. Community satisfaction is comprised of the factors that residents consider important to their happiness and impact their decisions about where they reside. Part of community satisfaction is the feeling the people of the community have toward the local organizations. Griffin (2011) describes job satisfaction as to how individuals are pleased with their jobs.

Furthermore, "community attachment is a personal reaction to departure from the community. Residents within rural communities consider the attachment they have to the area. This could be especially evident in those residents who have children. While the caretaker(s) of the dependents may desire to move when they consider their attachments to the community through their children, their decision to relocate may be altered. Another example of community attachment is the bond parents have with grown children residing in the area (Hanaysha, 2016).

Job satisfaction is a very important attribute that organizations frequently measure. It is a recurring attitude and therefore needs continuous management. The drive to understand and explain job satisfaction has been motivated by useful and practical reasons. It could increase productivity, enhance organizational commitment, lower absenteeism, and turnover, and ultimately increase organizational effectiveness.

C. *Metacognitive Awareness*

Metacognition is the ability to think about one's thoughts and regulate them. Teaching metacognitive strategies can improve the performance of students, which makes it a good target for action based on evidence. Such thoughts control the ability to change them. It is a leap beyond basic comprehension of thought patterns, integrating the ability to change thoughts and behaviors (Beisler&Medaille, 2015).

Metacognition includes thinking and thinking before, during, and after the task of learning. Once students think about their methods to perform a task, metacognition begins. When they choose the most effective strategies, metacognition occurs and determine for themselves whether the result of these strategies meets the standards (De Backer et al., 2016). It is the awareness and management of one's thoughts (Smith & Mancy, 2018; Azevedo, 2015) and the monitoring and control of thought.

It refers to knowledge about oneself and about what influences one's performance. Moreover, it involves knowledge, skills, and strategies essential for accomplishing a task under various conditions (Mahdavi, 2014). In other words, declarative knowledge refers to the understanding that a person may have about their abilities and the salient learning characteristics that affect cognitive processing (Iwai, 2011).

Moreover, declarative knowledge is knowledge about what one knows (Sugiharto et al., 2018). It is the knowledge of how to learn and the factors that encourage the learning process (Arkorful&Abaidoo, 2015). It is concerned with the insights of a person about their ability to process learning and the factors which influence their performance (De Backer et al., 2012). Further, this type of knowledge is easily noticed, for instance, when a person is mindful of the breach between their understanding and the demands of the transcript.

In the same vein, procedural knowledge refers to the awareness of applying procedures as learning strategies to utilize declarative knowledge and achieve goals (Harris et al., 2016). When someone knows how to do things and procedures, such as learning strategies, skilled learners possess more intuitive, accurate, and sufficient procedural knowledge than unskilled learners. Similarly, procedural knowledge refers to knowledge about the execution of procedural skills. Individuals with a high degree of procedural knowledge use skills more automatically (Schraw & Moshman, 1995). It necessitates learners to understand what reading strategies are and how to use them (Iwai, 2011).

It is also known as the knowledge of efficient methods, procedural knowledge aimed at achieving particular learning goals, and the cognizance of how to apply cognitive skills in the learning process (De Backer et al., 2012). Knowledge of methods that can be used to achieve success will provide security for a person facing problems. The assurance of answering learning-related problems grows within the ability of the person to apply their cognitive skills. Further, it is the knowledge about the approaches that can improve performance (Sugiharto et al., 2018).

It is the knowledge of when and why to apply various procedures, skills, and cognitive actions or strategies. Moreover, this is related to knowing when and why declarative and procedural knowledge is used. It is appropriate to add that the conditional knowledge of efficacious learners makes them facile and flexible in their strategy use (Asy' ari et al., 2019).

Conditional knowledge is usually associated with knowledge of external conditions or set up so that the use and effectiveness of particular strategies can be fitting to those circumstances (De Backer et al., 2012). Conditional knowledge is indulgent of when and how to use something we already know, for example, using different strategies in different situations (Sugiharto et al., 2018).

Moreover, conditional knowledge is the awareness of how, when, and where to use particular strategies (McDermott & Hand, 2013). Conditional knowledge emphasizes knowledge that links facts to employ inductive reasoning, making a decision based on facts collected together (Sugiharto et al., 2018).

This refers to the assortment of proper strategies and providing resources sufficient for reaching goals (Mahdavi, 2014). More importantly, planning provides a structure and

context for both teachers and students and the framework for evaluation (Spencer et al., 2012). Planning entails thinking about the future and trying to assume control over the future events by consolidating and managing resources so they can gratify the successful completion of the set forth objectives (Bandarin, 2016). Thus, effective teaching results from planning and enhancing student performance and achievement (Blazer, 2009).

On the other hand, monitoring can be understood as an act of cognition and can be tacit within the more general context of self-regulation. For example, individuals who are successful in life tend to know what they need and want, set goals for themselves, and make plans to achieve these goals (Ylvisaker, 2005). Conscientious teachers regularly self-evaluate their teaching strategies and instructional techniques (Koszycki et al., 2010). Hence, self-appraisal is one useful indicator of competence and professionalism, which involves reviewing current knowledge, skills, and attitudes to improve teaching. Moreover, it implies the importance of reflective reviewing or monitoring (Rani et al., 2017).

Evaluation refers to examining the progress made toward goals, triggering further planning, monitoring, and evaluation (Mahdavi, 2014). Also, evaluation is closely connected to planning and monitoring reflection-in-action and reflection-on-action. Continually evaluating the performance of both the students and teachers is beneficial to identify learning needs and respond accordingly (Berry, 2008).

A teacher who can employ the use of teaching about thinking has reached a superior level of metacognitive thinking for students — planning a course of action before beginning a task, monitoring themselves during the execution of a plan, backing up or adjusting a plan consciously, and evaluating themselves upon completion (Hargrove, 2013). Teaching about thinking incorporates the need for thinking out loud for others to understand the thought processes taking place within one's mind, providing others with the ability to make connections to their thinking about their thinking. In layman's terms, research focuses on a person's ability to plan, monitor, and evaluate metacognition (Darling-Hammond et al., 2018).

The basis of teaching about thinking is the evaluation and reflection portion of our metacognition. When evaluating, teachers need to show their evaluation and reflection strategies by going back to their work and honing in on critical aspects of their work that they feel need refining or revising to assist students with thinking about their thinking (Marks & Fraley, 2007).

Metacognition is the ability of learners to take necessary steps to plan suitable strategies for solving the problems they face, evaluate consequences and outcomes, and modify the approach as needed, based on the use of their prior knowledge. Metacognition helps learners successfully achieve a personal goal by choosing the right cognitive tool for this purpose.

D. Correlation between Measures

Organizational commitment can be thought of as an extension of job satisfaction. It deals with the teacher's positive attitude, not toward her job but the organization. The emotions, however, are much stronger in the case of organizational commitment. It is characterized by the teachers' attachment to the organization and readiness to make sacrifices for the organization (Govender & Parumasur, 2010).

According to Day (2011), teacher commitment is multidimensional. They can feel the commitment to the organization, the students, their career continuance, the professional knowledge base, and the teaching profession. Commitment to the teaching becomes a reason of internal driving force for a good performance, and commitment to the institution becomes a stronger motivational force for admirable work. Job commitment is an emotional attachment to the job and organization. Hassan et al. (2018) has described job commitment in three aspects. Firstly, affective commitment (love for the job) is a strong emotional attachment to a job/organization that increases job satisfaction. Secondly, continuance commitment (fear of job loss) is a fear of loss that could be greater than the benefit one can get out of the new job. Thirdly, normative commitment (obligation to stay at a job) is the state of mind where the employee feels that he should stay with the organization (Balci, 2007).

Teacher commitment is recognized by Srisrankulwong (2005) as an intrinsic quality of a good teacher. It reflects job satisfaction, morale, motivation, identity, and professional meaning. Committed teachers will work devotedly for the values and school goals and engage in promoting the development and well-being of the students; teachers are committed to both the organization and the profession in successful schools (Guay, 2008). Teachers' metacognitive attitude is a strong predictor of an effective teaching motivation, confirming the study of Caprara et al. (2006), which emphasizes that teachers' beliefs in their capacity to manage class situations, didactical tasks efficaciously, and interpersonal relationships with the other school members strongly influences their level of satisfaction with job conditions and likely, the morale of the whole school as resulting from aggregated teachers' job satisfaction (Bembeanutty, 2007).

Buchanan (2006) strives to describe the relation between job satisfaction and performance, keeping this relation's value for organizations. Three factors generally determine individual performance. Motivation, the desire to do the job, ability, the capability to do the job, and the work environment, the tools, materials, and information needed to do the job. If an employee lacks the ability, the manager can provide training or replace the worker. If there is an environmental problem, the manager can also make adjustments to promote higher performance. But if motivation is the problem, the manager's task is more challenging. Individual behavior is a complex phenomenon, and the manager may not be able to figure out why the employee is not motivated and how to change

the behavior. Thus, also motivation plays a vital role since it might negatively influence performance and because of its intangible nature.

If your employees are satisfied, they will produce superior quality performance in optimal time and lead to growing profits. Satisfied teachers are also more likely to be creative and innovative and come up with breakthroughs that allow an institution to grow and change positively with time and market conditions. The quality or effectiveness of teachers is associated with their satisfaction with their profession and their satisfaction with their values. Thus, it is clear that an effective and competent teacher will achieve the desired learning outcomes, provided he is satisfied in his profession or job (Wright & Crapanzano, 2007).

Committed teachers are likely to be devoted to the teaching profession and the organization, thus giving the best of themselves to their work resulting in efficient utilization of time and resources. Satisfied teachers who are organizationally committed are likely to have a good attendance record and adhere to school policies (Gumussoy, 2007).

Organizational commitment is how a teacher feels loyalty to a particular organization. Thus, organizational commitment acts as a psychological link to an organization that influences individuals to act consistently with the organization's interests (Yang, 2002).

Teachers' involvement and commitment are essential for successfully implementing strategic change in organizations (Fiegener, 2005; Elbanna, 2012). It can be said that companies can demand that employees make strategic changes involving as many managers and employees as possible. Tonnessen and Jepsen (2009) argue that when employees understand the strategy of their company, they think they are members of the group and therefore increase their willingness to work towards common business goals.

The teachers' commitment is considered the principal indicator of failure or success in the education system. Due to the minimal commitment of the teachers, students tend to lose their level of self-efficacy. In this way, students switch to the deeper strategic approach to learning and move toward the surface learning approach in the first year of education (Stavrou et al., 2016).

Furthermore, the initial presentation and discussion of various literature have helped bring into focus the two important variables of the study; professional commitment and job satisfaction. These served as support to the results and findings of the study.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study employs the quantitative non – experimental design method of research using the correlation technique. The plan and structure of this research are to provide a credible answer to a research question. Its purpose is to describe obtainable characteristics such as achievement, attitudes, behavior, and relationships. The non – experimental quantitative method is appropriate for the present investigation because it deals with the mediating effect of metacognitive awareness on the relationship between professional commitment and job satisfaction. Variables are not manipulated; they are only identified and are studied as they occur in a natural setting (Educational Research, 2011).

The descriptive survey is valuable in proving facts on which scientific judgments may be based. It provides essential knowledge about the nature of objects and persons and plays a large part in the instruments' development for the measurements of many things. These instruments are engaged in all types of quantitative research as data-gathering instruments. The descriptive-correlational survey method is appropriate for the present investigation, for it deals with the description and determination of both independent and dependent variables (Creswell, 2008).

The mediating variable lies intermediate between causal factors and an outcome. It causes mediation in the dependent and independent variables. It further aims to estimate how a variable affects X's impact on Y. A mediator is presumed to cause the outcome and not vice versa. One reason for testing mediation is to understand how the initial variable affects the outcome (Baron & Kenny, 1986).

Further, a mediator can be a potential mechanism where an independent variable can cause changes in a dependent variable. Thus, the metacognitive awareness may function as a mediator when variations in the perceived school professional commitment and job satisfaction account for the variations in the metacognitive awareness. And the variations in metacognitive awareness significantly account for the variations in work engagement. And finally, the direct link between professional commitment and job satisfaction is no longer significant. The interest of the study is to investigate the relationship between professional commitment and job satisfaction, the relationship between professional commitment and job satisfaction, the relationship between metacognitive awareness and job satisfaction, and the mediating effect of metacognitive awareness on the relationship between professional commitment and job satisfaction of teachers.

These findings were specific to the context of the public elementary schools of Manay, Davao Oriental. The scope limits the possibility for the overall applicability of the results and the sample; accordingly, even though there

could be common structures, the findings may not have overall applicability to other systems.

The public elementary schools of Manay District, Davao Oriental, were chosen as the research setting. The scope limited the possibility for the general applicability of the findings and the sample; accordingly, even though there could be common features, the findings may not have general applicability to other systems.

The respondents in which public elementary schools of Manay District are located in the Municipality of Manay, Davao Oriental. Manay is a second-class municipality in the province.

The respondents were 300 public elementary school students in Manay District from 20 public elementary schools. Furthermore, the place of the respondents and the conduct of the study are located in the Municipality of Manay, Davao Oriental, Philippines.

Moreover, the researcher considered the inclusion and exclusion criteria in selecting the study's respondents. The teacher respondents are regular teachers among public elementary schools in Manay Central District, whose plantilla numbers are in the Department of Education. Teachers are willing to submit themselves and are permitted by their school heads to undergo the survey to be conducted. Those teachers who voluntarily agree with the informed consent are included in the survey; hence, teachers who confessed their denial are excluded from the study. Further, the researcher considers teachers who decided to withdraw or back out during the actual administration of the survey questionnaires.

The gathering of data used by the researcher has divided into three parts. The first part of the questionnaire deals with professional commitment. With Cronbach Alpha result of .877, which implies that the items have relatively high consistency, having subscales of the affective professional commitment (APC), continuance professional commitment (CPC), and normative professional commitment variable questionnaire was adapted from (Meyer et al., 1993). The second set of instruments used is to measure teachers' job satisfaction. The questionnaire is modified and patterned on the Asia Pacific Institute of Advanced Research (APIAR) (2018) study with a Cronbach Alpha result of .912, which implies that the items have relatively high consistency. With emphasis on the following indicators: security (salary, benefits, rewards, performance, recognition, and promotion), work environment; job responsibilities; and community attachments/ linkages. And, the third set was an adapted questionnaire from the Modified Version of Metacognitive Awareness Inventory for Teachers (MAIT) developed by (Zhou & Brown, 2017). It encompasses the six factors of Metacognitive Awareness. The validated survey questionnaire annexed to this paper be seen in the appendices part. Items were clustered under six pre-determined domains: declarative knowledge; procedural knowledge; conditional knowledge; planning; monitoring; and evaluating.), with a Cronbach Alpha result of .966,

which implies that the items have relatively high consistency.

Moreover, the adapted standardized questionnaire is valid in contents as they went through a series of modifications to classify the most reliable and valid questions. Further, it was already tested and proven by the authors per se. The questionnaire was designed in a very comprehensive form with the help of the expert validators to provide the respondents with ease and comfort in answering each question and understanding the study's objective. Upon validation, the questionnaire got an overall mean score of 4.28, equivalent to the expert validators' very good descriptive rating.

Also, pilot testing will also be applied. Cronbach alpha will be used to check the validity of the questionnaire with the following measures: cognitive awareness and professional commitment to job satisfaction. Cronbach's alpha consistency coefficient customarily ranges between zero to one. However, there was no lower limit to the coefficient. The closer the Cronbach's alpha coefficient to one, the larger the internal constancy of the items in the scale (Gliem&Gliem, 2003). There would be modifications to check the validity of the questionnaires.

In addition, the researcher asked permission from the office of the Superintendent of the Manay Davao Oriental to conduct the study among the different public elementary schools of Manay Davao Oriental. Upon approval, the letter of endorsement is sought to accommodate the researcher to administer the survey questionnaire to the study's respondents. Moreover, the researcher made another letter to conduct the study to teachers in their respective schools in Manay Davao Oriental. The researcher asked for the School Heads' approval to distribute survey questionnaires to their respective teachers. The researcher personally handed in the questionnaire and explained the research tool and its purpose.

Furthermore, the researcher retrieved the survey questionnaires after the respondents had answered all items. Finally, the researcher tallied and tabulated all the

data gathered from the respondents and subjected them to statistical analysis. The statistical results are analyzed and interpreted. With the data, conclusions were drawn, and recommendations were formulated based on the study's findings.

The statistical tools that are employed by the researcher in the analysis and interpretation of the data are mean which was used to determine the level of professional commitment, teacher job satisfaction, and metacognitive awareness to answer problems 1, 2, and 3; Pearson r was utilized to determine if the relationship between professional commitment and teacher job satisfaction, professional commitment ,metacognitive awareness, and metacognitive awareness and teacher job satisfaction are significant; and path analysis was employed to prove the mediation and strengthen the obtained result.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the acquired data are depicted in this part of the paper based on the research objectives of this study. The flow of presentation on the stated topic is as follows: level of professional commitment, level of job satisfaction, and level of metacognitive awareness; the correlation between professional commitment and job satisfaction; the correlation between metacognitive awareness and job satisfaction.

Shown in Table 1 are the average scores for the indicators of professional commitment, with an overall mean of 4.13 described as high with a standard deviation of 0.42. The high level could be attributed to the equally high rating given by the respondents. The cited overall mean score was the result gathered from the computed mean scores of its indicators. The data could glean the indicator with the highest mean rating of 4.13 or high are affective professional commitment with a mean score of 0.49 and normative professional commitment with a mean score of 0.36. In contrast, the indicator with the lowest mean rating of 4.12, still high, is continuance professional commitment with a mean score of 0.54.

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Affective	0.49	4.13	High
Continuance	0.54	4.12	High
Normative	0.36	4.13	High
Overall	0.42	4.13	High

Table 1: Professional Commitment

The data shows that the high level of professional commitment is due to the high rating given by the respondents on the importance of affective professional commitment (APC), continuance professional commitment, and normative professional commitment; these indicators registered an overall high rating which was the product of the high scores rated by the teachers. This indicates that competent and committed teachers are one of the most crucial factors in the success of any education system. A teacher who is truly committed to

their profession puts students' learning and interests above everything else (Gaan, 2008). This finding conforms with the pronouncement of Levy (2011), which stated that the teachers were professionals and committed to the teaching profession. They felt proud of the teaching profession.

In the same vein, McMahon and Hoy (2009) said that the strong belief and acceptance of goals and professional values and the will to make considerable efforts to fulfill the professional objectives and responsibilities. Along with

their professional experience, teachers effectively involve themselves in their activity, establishing effective relationships with peers and students.

The second objective was to determine the level of job satisfaction which was measured through a survey questionnaire with the following indicators are security; work environment; job responsibilities; and community

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Security	0.29	3.97	High
Work Environment	0.31	4.01	High
Job Responsibility	0.31	3.90	High
Community Attachments/Linkages	0.34	4.10	High
Overall	0.27	4.00	High

Table 2: Job Satisfaction

In contrast, job responsibility is the indicator with the lowest mean rating of 3.90 but still high. The two other indicators work environment got a mean score of 4.01 with a standard deviation of 0.31; and, security with a mean score of 3.97 and a standard deviation of 0.29.

As rated by the respondents, the high level of job satisfaction, these indicators registered an overall very high rating, which was the product of the very high scores rated by the teachers. This indicates that every teacher must have the potential and clear intention to discharge their duty with utmost devotion to derive satisfaction from their work. Job satisfaction is the combination of emotional and psychological experience at any work. Job Satisfaction is the relationship between what everyone expects according to what everyone achieves. Any work cannot be effectively done without satisfaction

The viewpoints of various authors, including Olorube (2008); Ghosh (2015); Kavita (2013), said that teachers' job satisfaction is the sense of fulfilment and pride felt by people who enjoy their work and do it well. Job satisfaction is also how a job provides gratification, actualization, and enjoyment to the worker. Job

attachment/linkages. Shown in Table 2 are the data on the level of job satisfaction. Computations yield a grand mean of 4.00 or high with a standard deviation of 0.27, indicating that job satisfaction is always manifested. It could be gleaned from the data that the indicator with the highest mean rating of 4.10 or high is community attachment/linkages.

satisfaction is also used to refer to the degree to which a teacher is happy with their success in meeting their career goals and expectation.

The third objective was to determine the level of metacognitive awareness, which was measured through a survey questionnaire. Shown in Table 3 are the data on the level of metacognitive awareness. Computations yield a grand mean of 4.17 or high with a standard deviation of 0.37, indicating that metacognitive awareness is oftentimes manifested. The high level of metacognitive awareness is due to the high ratings given by the respondents. This implies that the teachers possess the necessary knowledge, skills, and strategies for accomplishing tasks under various conditions; they display a high metacognitive awareness (Mahdavi, 2014). These practices, therefore, are expected to increase understanding of their abilities and the salient learning characteristics that affect cognitive processing since it is in line with the views of various authors (Iwai, 2011; Mahdavi, 2014; Spencer et al., 2012) who stated that teachers need to progress in providing structure, as well as the framework and evaluation.

Metacognitive Awareness	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Overall	0.37	4.17	High

Table 3: Extent of Metacognitive Awareness

Illustrated in Table 4 is the test result on the relationship between the variables. The result shows that the overall values reveal a positive and significant relationship between professional commitment and job satisfaction. The overall result reflects that professional commitment is positively correlated with job satisfaction since the overall r-value is .874 with a p-value $p < 0.01$, hence rejecting the null hypothesis. Hence, there is a positive association between the two variables.

In particular, it revealed a positive and significant relationship between all indicators of professional commitment and job satisfaction, as revealed in the P-value of less than 0.05, and with an r-value of .848 on security, .689 on the work environment, .694 on job responsibilities, and .805 on community attachments/linkages, with an overall value of 874.

Pair	Variables		p-value	Decision on Ho
IV and DV	Professional Commitment and Job Satisfaction	.874*	0.000	Reject
IV and MV	Professional Commitment and Meta Cognitive Awareness	.719*	0.000	Reject
MV and DV	Meta Cognitive Awareness and Job Satisfaction	.812*	0.000	Reject

Table 4: Relationship between the variables

The present study reveals a significant relationship between professional commitment and job satisfaction. This implies that a teacher’s professional commitment influences job satisfaction, as seen in the data. This confirms the study of Wright and Crapanzano (2007) that satisfied teachers are also more likely to be creative and innovative and come up with breakthroughs that allow an institution to grow and change positively with time and changing market conditions. The quality or effectiveness of teachers is associated with their satisfaction with their profession and their satisfaction with their values. Thus, it is clear that an effective and competent teacher will achieve the desired learning outcomes, provided he is satisfied in his profession or job.

Moreover, the test result on the relationship between professional commitment metacognitive awareness as shown Table 4 as well. This relationship was tested at a 0.05 level of significance. In particular, it revealed a positive and significant relationship between all indicators of professional commitment and metacognitive awareness, as revealed in the p-value of less than 0.05 and with an r-value of .699 for affective professional commitment, .682 for continuance professional commitment, and .633 on normative professional commitment, with an overall value of 719. When all indicators, professional commitment, are correlated with the indicators of metacognitive awareness, all r- values were greater than p<0.05 significant level, hence, significant.

To sum it up, professional commitment and metacognitive awareness show a moderate positive relationship; this implies that professional commitment has something to do with metacognitive awareness. So, if the professional commitment improves, the teachers gain awareness about and control over how they think and teach by planning, monitoring, evaluating, and adjusting their instructional goals and teaching strategies according to their student’s needs and the sociocultural context. The present study reveals a significant relationship between professional commitment and metacognitive awareness. This implies that professional commitment significantly

influences metacognitive awareness, as seen in the data. This confirms the study of Takallou (2011) stressed that committed teachers are concerned with their students’ development and profoundly struggle with how to keep students learning. They cultivate students’ curiosity and interest in learning. Showing commitment to student learning can be an important factor in motivating students. Committed teachers recognize and endeavor to fulfill their responsibilities to their students. The degree of loyalty committed teachers to have toward their profession is one of their distinguishing characteristics.

As for the result of the test on the relationship between metacognitive awareness and job satisfaction. In particular, it revealed a positive and significant relationship between all indicators of metacognitive awareness and job satisfaction, as revealed in the P-value of less than 0.05, and with an r-value of .728 on security, .647 on the work environment, .676 on job responsibilities and .766 on community attachments/linkages, with an overall value of 812. The overall result reflects that metacognitive awareness is positively correlated with job satisfaction since the overall r-value is .812 with a p-value <.05, hence rejecting the null hypothesis. This shows that the increase in metacognitive awareness would also likely increase job satisfaction.

The test of the relationship between metacognitive awareness and job satisfaction revealed a significant relationship between metacognitive awareness and job satisfaction. This implies that metacognitive awareness is correlated to job satisfaction. In other words, teachers feel positive emotions during teaching, use different teaching strategies according to the classroom and the students, and have a good self-efficacy perception about their work. This result conforms to the result of Caprara et al. (2006) which emphasized that teachers’ beliefs in their capacity to manage class situations, didactical tasks efficaciously, and interpersonal relationships with the other school members strongly influence their satisfaction with job conditions and, likely, the morale of the whole school as resulting from aggregated teachers’ job satisfaction.

Path	Estimates		SE	C.R.	P
	Unstandardized	Standardized			
PC to MCA	.666	.749	.034	19.543	***
MCA to JS	.264	.358	.027	9.637	***
PC to JS	.396	.605	.024	16.278	***

Table 5: Mediating Effect: Path Analysis

Legend: X=Professional Commitment (PC)
 Y= Job Satisfaction (JS)
 M=Meta cognitive Awareness (MCA)

Shown in Table 5 is the regression analysis of the mediating effect of meta cognitive awareness on the relationship between professional commitment and job satisfaction. As evident in the study of Baron and Kenny (1986), there are three steps to be met for a third variable to be acting as a mediator. These are categorized as steps 1 to 3, and step 4 is the final step as shown in Figure 1. In Step 1 (Path C), professional commitment as an independent variable (IV) significantly predicts job satisfaction, the dependent variable (DV). In Step 2 (Path A), the engagement of students (IV) significantly predicts metacognitive awareness, the mediator (MV).

In Step 3, the mediator (MV), metacognitive awareness, significantly predicts job satisfaction. In Step 4, the combined effect of professional commitment and metacognitive awareness on job satisfaction is significant. Lastly, the figure shows the results of the computation of the effect size in the mediation test conducted between the three variables. The effect size measures how much of the effect of job satisfaction on metacognitive awareness can

be attributed to the indirect path with a $p < 0.01$, which is significant. The total effect value of $p < 0.01$ is the raw correlation between metacognitive awareness and job satisfaction with $p < 0.01$, signifying no mediation and significance since $p < 0.01$ is less than .05. Applying the principle of Multiple Regression is appropriate because the data has passed the preliminary analysis by establishing a high level of correlation of $p < 0.01$. Apart from the assumption of normality of data, a high level of correlation among the variables is required to do away with a spurious model.

Furthermore, the study results also suggest that there is also a partial mediation on the effect of mediating effect of metacognitive awareness and professional commitment on job satisfaction. This implies that metacognitive awareness influences professional commitment, which influences job satisfaction. This further strengthens the validity of the theory presented in this study, in which the results of each regression between two variables support the authors in the framework.

Fig. 1: Path Analysis between Variables

The finding of this study supported the pronouncement of Fiegner (2005), and Elbanna (2012), who stated that teachers' involvement and commitment are essential for the successful implementation of strategic change in organizations. It can be said that companies can demand that employees make strategic changes involving as many managers and employees as possible. This study also supported the proposition of Adesoji (2008), which states that teaching style is also associated with a sense of confidence in students and understanding of the purpose of education in general. Teachers who practice this style will serve as helpful mentors and can tolerate students. Teachers also believe in the best ways for students to learn about learning.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

While the overall results of the study revealed high levels, despite the rich body of prior research on student engagement, additional studies are needed to analyze the patterns of change in the levels of student engagement from the longitudinal perspective. These studies should not only seek to measure student engagement but provide interventions that address certain factors influencing

engagement and estimate the effects the interventions would produce in the level of engagement within time. Many of the existing studies aimed to estimate the causal links between student engagement, motivation, and academic outcomes. As these links were proved to be rather clear, it becomes more relevant to empirically seek ways to control student engagement levels to reach the desired academic outcomes.

Since there is a high level of metacognitive awareness, it is recommended for them to have subjects focused on enhancing the metacognitive awareness of their soon-to-be teachers. Since if metacognitive awareness is harnessed in the undergraduate years of these aspiring teachers, being proactive with initiating how to go about the strategies in teaching will be natural to them

Teachers will have to adorn a special hat of a motivator in pandemic learning modes, akin to a cement mixer! A motivator who facilitates the right mix of tasks and flexible grading schemes and couples them up with the right mix of online collaborative technology to churn out positive energy and a great learning experience for students. Thus, it will depend on the students' motivational

energy fed back to the teacher via their constructive progress, response, and enthusiasm.

VI. CONCLUSION

With consideration of the study's findings, conclusions are drawn in this section. The respondent, public school teachers, exhibited a very high level of professional commitment, high level of student engagement, and high level of professional roles and expertise. The study results also confirm that there is a significant relationship between teaching style and professional roles and expertise. Similarly, there is a significant relationship between professional roles and expertise and student engagement. A significant relationship also exists between teaching style and student engagement.

Lastly, the study results suggest that professional roles and expertise significantly and partially mediate the relationship between teaching style and student engagement. Rather than a direct causal relationship between professional roles and expertise and student engagement, the result revealed that the former influences the professional roles and expertise, which influences the latter variable.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The researcher wishes to express his deepest gratefulness and admiration to the following persons who contributed to the success of this study.

To Almighty Father, the source of all wisdom, strength, making all things possible for the researcher to overcome all the difficulties in accomplishing this study; His adviser, for opening his eyes to new stages of opportunity and strength, for adding smiles to faces and for guiding towards the right path; His panel members, for their comments, constructive criticism, corrections and suggestions to improve his study.

To the Department of Education, Division of Mati City, for allowing the researcher to conduct the study; The Mati Central District Teachers for their valuable time, effort and cooperation in answering the questionnaire. The researcher's co-teachers, co-researchers and friends for encouraging the researcher to continue his studies.

Finally, his family and Loved ones to whom he lovingly dedicates this journey, his loved ones for every word of encouragement to fight and surpass all hardships and trials, his very supportive father and mother who always there in terms of difficulties, undying moral and financial support which made all things possible for the success of his study.

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REFERENCES

- [1.] Adesoji, F. A. (2008). Managing students' attitude towards science through problem – solving instructional strategy. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09720073.2008.11891024>
- [2.] Alsop, R., &Heinsohn, N. (2015). Measuring empowerment in practice: structuring analysis and framing indicators. *World* (1), 123.
- [3.] Apasu, Y. (2011). Identifying the antecedents of salespersons intention to leave. *Akron Business and Economic Review*, 17(4), 85-97.
- [4.] Arkorful, G.T., &Abaidoo, F.G. (2015). Identifying influences on attitudes and self –efficacy beliefs towards technology integration among pre-service educators: *Electronic Journal for the integration of technology in Education*, 6, 28-42
- [5.] Asia Pacific Institute of Advanced Research (APIAR) (2018). *Asia Pacific Journal of Contemporary Education and Communication Technology (APJCECT)* ISBN: 978 0 9943656 82; ISSN: 2205-618. <https://apiar.org.au/journal/asia-pacific-journal-of-contemporary-education-and-communication-technology/>
- [6.] Asy'ari M, Ikhsan M, &Muhali, K.L. (2019) The effectiveness of inquiry learning model in improving prospective teachers' metacognition knowledge and metacognition awareness. *Int. J. Instr.*, 12 (2) 455–470
- [7.] Azevedo, R. (2015). Computer environments as metacognitive tools for enhancing learning. *Educational Psychologist*, 40(4), 193–197. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15326985ep4004_1
- [8.] Balci, A. (2007). Comparison of performance feedback procedures on teachers' treatment implementation integrity and students' inappropriate behavior in special education classrooms. *Journal of Applied Behavior Analysis*, 40, 447–461.
- [9.] Bandarin, R. Y. (2016). The impact of procedural and epistemological knowledge on conceptual understanding: the case of density and floating–sinking phenomena. *Instructional Science*, 1, 20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11251-016-9375-z>
- [10.] Baron, R. M., & Kenny, D. A. (1986). The moderator-mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51, 1173-1182
- [11.] Beisler, M., &Medaille, A. (2016). How do students get help with research assignments? Using drawings

- to understand students' help seeking behavior. *Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 42(4), 390–400.
- [12.] Bembanutty, H. (2007). Pre-service teachers' motivational beliefs and self-regulation of learning. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED496521>
- [13.] Berry, M. G. (2008). . Spanking and child outcomes: Old controversies and new meta-analyses. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 30(4), 453–469. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/fam0000191>.
- [14.] Blazer, D. S. (2009). Metacognitive awareness and academic achievement in college students. *Journal of the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning*, 8(2), 1–10.
- [15.] Brown, K. M., & Wynn, S. R. (2009). Finding, Supporting and Keeping: the role of principal in teacher retention issues. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 8, 37-63. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/15700760701817371>
- [16.] Buchanan, R. (2006). Intervention selection in school psychology: Using public health models to enhance systems capacity of schools. *School Psychology Review*, 35, 167-180.
- [17.] Caprara, G. V., Barbaranelli, C., Steca, P., & Malone, P. S. (2006). Teachers' self-efficacy beliefs as determinants of job satisfaction and students' academic achievement: A study at the school level. *Journal of School Psychology*, 44(6), 473–490. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsp.2006.09.001>
- [18.] Chaney, C. A. (2017). Work-life variables influencing attrition among beginning agriscience teachers of Texas (Doctoral dissertation). <http://repositories.tdl.org/>
- [19.] Chen, C. (2010). Why so unhappy? The effect of unionization on job satisfaction. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 72, 357-380.
- [20.] Cho, V., & Huang, X. (2012). Professional commitment, organizational commitment, and the intention to leave for professional advancement. *Information Technology & People*, 25(1), 31-54. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/09593841211204335>
- [21.] Creswell, J. W. (2008). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research* (3rd ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Education, Inc.
- [22.] Croom, D. B. (2003). Teacher burnout in agricultural education. *Journal of Agricultural Education*, 44(2), 1-13. [doi:10.5032/jae.2003.020adeso01](https://doi.org/10.5032/jae.2003.020adeso01)
- [23.] Darling-Hammond, L., Cook-Harvey, C., Flook, L., Gardner, M., & Melnick, H. (2018). *With the whole child in mind: Insights from the corner school development program*. Alexandria, VA: ASCD
- [24.] Day, C. (2011). 'Building and sustaining successful principalship in England: The importance of trust.' *Journal of Educational Administration*, 47(6), 719–730.
- [25.] Day, C., Sammons, P., Stobart, G., Kington, A., & Gu, Q. (2007). *Teachers matter: Connecting lives, work and effectiveness*. Maidenhead: OpenUniversity Press.
- [26.] De Backer, J., Van Keer, S., & Valcke, T.O. (2012). Parasocial relationships and self-discrepancies: Faux relationships have benefits for low self-esteem individuals. *Personal Relationships*, 15, 261–280. [doi:10.1111/j.1475-6811.2008.00197](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-6811.2008.00197).
- [27.] De Backer, L., Van Keer, H., Moerkerke, B., & Valcke, M. (2016). Examining evolutions in the adoption of metacognitive regulation in reciprocal peer tutoring groups. *Metacognition and Learning*, 11(2), 187–213. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11409-015-9141-7>
- [28.] Delima, V. T. (2015). Professional identity, professional commitment and teachers' performance. *International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning*, 2(4), 1-12.
- [29.] Demir, K. (2015). The effect of organizational trust on the culture of teacher leadership in primary schools. *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice*, 15(3), 621-634.
- [30.] Denton, D. J. (2019). Sex differences in satisfaction with pay and co-workers: faculty and staff at a public institution. *Public Personnel Management*, 28(3), 345-349.
- [31.] Educational Research (2011). *Social-Psychological interventions in education: They're not magic*. New York: Routledge. <http://rer.sagepub.com/content/81/2/267>
- [32.] Elbanna, S. (2012) Slack, planning, and organizational performance: Evidence from the Arab Middle East. *European Management Review*, 9 (2), 99-115.
- [33.] Fiegener, M. K. (2005). Determinants of board participation in the strategic decisions of small corporations. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 29(5), 627-650.
- [34.] Gaan, N. (2008). Stress, social support, job attitudes and job outcome across gender. *The Icfai University Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 52, 34-44.
- [35.] Ghosh, D. (2015). Do commitment based human resource practices influence job embeddedness and intention to quit? *IIMB Management Review*, 27(4), 240–251. [doi:10.1016/j.iimb.2015.09.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iimb.2015.09.003).
- [36.] Ghosh, P. (2016). Support at work to fuel engagement: A study of employees of Indian banking sector. *Review of Integrative Business & Economic Research*, 5 (2), 1 – 10.
- [37.] Gliem J.A., & Gliem R.R. (2003). Calculating, interpreting, and reporting cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient for likert-type scales. <https://scholarworks.iupui.edu/handle/1805/344>
- [38.] Govaerts, N., Kyndt, E., Dochy, F., & Baert, H. (2011). Influence of learning and working climate on the retention of talented employees". *Journal of Workplace Learning*, 23 (1), 35-55. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13665621111097245>
- [39.] Govender, S., & Parumasur, S. B. (2010). Impact of global financial crisis on job satisfaction of employees of Nigerian banks. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Review*, 2(2), 14-18.

- [40.] Griffin M. (2011). Job satisfaction and teamwork: The role of supervisor support. *J. Org. Behav.* 22, 537-550
- [41.] Guay, K.P. (2008). . Stretching the limits in help-seeking research: Theoretical, methodological, and technological advances. *Learning and Instruction*, 21(2), 243–246. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2010.07.002>
- [42.] Gumussoy, H. O. (2007). Moving into the third, outer domain of teacher satisfaction. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 38, 379–396.
- [43.] Guven, M. (2011). Meta-cognitive strategy usage and epistemological beliefs of primary school teacher trainees. ISSN: ISSN-1303-0485. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ919889>
- [44.] Hanaysha, J. (2016). Testing the effects of employee engagement, work environment and organizational learning on organizational commitment. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 229, 289–297. doi:10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.07.139
- [45.] Hansen, J. R. (2017). Comparing affective commitment in the public and private sectors: A comprehensive test of multiple mediation effects. *International Public Management Journal*, 21, 558-588. doi:10.1080/10967494.2016.1276033
- [46.] Hargrove R. A. (2013). Assessing the long-term impact of a metacognitive approach to creative skill development. *Int. J. Technol. Des. Educ.* 23, 489–517. 10.1007/s10798-011-9200-6.
- [47.] Harris, K.R., Graham, S., Friedlander, C., & Laud, L. (2016). Self-regulated learning processes and children’s writing. B. Zimmerman & D.H. Schunk (Eds.), *Handbook of self-regulation of learning and performance* (pp. 187-202). London, UK: Routledge Publishers.
- [48.] Hassan, N., Yaakod, S.A., Mat Halif, R., Adbul Majid, A., & Sumardi, N. A. (2018). The effects of technostress creators and organizational commitment among school teachers. doi:10.24191/ajue.v15i3.7563
- [49.] Islam, T., Ali, G., & Ahmed, I. (2018). Protecting healthcare through organizational support to reduce turnover intention. *International Journal of Human Rights in Healthcare*, 11 (1), 4-12. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJHRH-03-2017-0012>
- [50.] Iwai, N. (2011). Facilitating collaborative knowledge construction. In *Proceedings of the 36th Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS)* (p. 10). <https://doi.org/10.1109/HICSS.2003.1173636>
- [51.] Jamal, W.O. (2018). Motivation, incentives and organizational culture. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 11(6), 28–38. doi:10.1108/13673270710832145.
- [52.] Kardes, G. (2009). How commitment both enables and undermines marketing relationships. *European Journal of Marketing*, 39 (11/12), 1372-1388.
- [53.] Kardes, G. (2019). Perceived high-performance work systems and subjective well-being. *Journal of Career Development*, 43(2), 116-129, doi: 10.1177/0894845315583113.
- [54.] Kavita, S. L. (2016). Does engagement of employees affect to organizational commitment? Evidence from non-academics in Sri Lankan state universities. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 6(2), 35–47
- [55.] Khuong, M. N., & Vu, P. L. (2014). Measuring the effects of drivers organizational commitment through the mediation of job satisfaction: A study in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. *International Journal of Current Research and Academic Review*, 2(2), 1–16
- [56.] Koszycki, D., Raab, K., Aldosary, F., & Bradwejn, J. (2010). A multifaceted spiritually based intervention for generalized anxiety disorder: A pilot randomized trial. *Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 66(4), 430–441.
- [57.] Levy, P. (2011). Setting social strategy. *Marketing News*, 45(3), 4. <http://www.ama.org/>
- [58.] Loganathan, C., & Dharmaraj, A. (2017). A study on impact of HRM practices and policies on employee’s organisational commitment in textile spinning mills in Tamil Nadu, India. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 10, 15. doi:10.17485/ijst/2017/v10i15/114239
- [59.] Mahdavi, H. (2014). Exploring the correlation between metacognition and cognitive retention of student using some biology teaching strategies. *Journal of Baltic Science Education*, 15(5), 617–629.
- [60.] Marks, M. J., & Fraley, R. C. (2007). The sexual double standard: Fact or fiction? *Sex Roles*, 52, 175–186
- [61.] McCready, L.T., Soloway, U. & Geoffrey, B. (2010). Teachers' perceptions of challenging student behaviours in model inner city schools. *Emotional and Behavioural Difficulties*, 15 (2), p111-123
- [62.] McDermott, H., & Hand, S. (2013). Social influence of an international celebrity: Responses to the death of Princess Diana. *Journal of Communication*, 53, 587–605. doi:10.1111/j.1460-2466.2003.tb02912.x
- [63.] McMahan, E., & Hoy, W. K. (2009). Professionalism in teaching: Toward a structural theory of professionalism. In W. K. Hoy & M. DiPaola (eds.), *Studies in school improvement*. Greenwich, CN: Information Age.
- [64.] McMahan S. D., Coker C., & Parnes A. L. (2013). Environmental stressors, social support, and internalizing symptoms among African American youth. *J. Community Psychol.* 41, 615–630. 10.1002/jcop.21560
- [65.] Meyer, J. P. (2014). Organizational commitment. In Guest, D.E & Needle, D. (Eds), *Human Resource Management*, (Vol. 5 of the *Wiley Encyclopedia of Management* (199–201), 3rd ed., Chichester, UK: Wiley
- [66.] Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J. (1991). A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human Resource Management Review*, 1(1), 61–89.
- [67.] Meyer, J. P., Allen, N. J., & Smith, C. A. (1993). Commitment to organisations and occupations: Extension and test of a three-component

- conceptualization. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 78,538–551.
- [68.] Ng, T. W. H. (2015). The incremental validity of organizational commitment, organizational trust, and organizational identification. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 88, 154-163.
- [69.] Northouse, P. G. (2010). *Leadership: Theory and practice* (5th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- [70.] Oh, I.-S., Blau, G., Han, J. H., & Kim, S. (2017). Human capital factors affecting human resource (HR) managers' commitment to HR and the mediating role of perceived organizational value on HR. *Human Resource Management*, 56(2), 353–368. doi:10.1002/hrm.2017.56.issue-2
- [71.] Ozutku, W.P. (2018). Affective, continuance, and normative commitment to the organization: a Meta-analysis of antecedents, correlates, and consequences. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 61(1), 20-52.
- [72.] Porter, J.R., Xie, L., Challinor, A.J., Cochrane, K., Howden, M., Iqbal, M.M., Lobell, D.B., Travasso, M.I., (2014). Chapter 7. Food security and food production systems. Working Group II Contribution to the IPCC 5th Assessment Report, Geneva, Switzerland.
https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2018/02/WGIAR5-Chap7_FINAL.pdf
- [73.] Rani, R. T., Ignatious, Y. H. ,Hari,F. O., & Balavishnu,E.D. (2017). Assessing parenting practices through parent-report and direct observation during parent-training. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 15(5), 554–567. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10826-006-9029-x>.
- [74.] Rehman, K. Z.U. (2015). Impacts of job satisfaction on organization commitment: A theoretical model for academicians in HEL of developing countries like Pakistan. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Science*, 80-89.
- [75.] Rico, R., & Ertmer, P. A. (2015). Examining the role of the instructor in problem-centered instruction. *Tech Trends: Linking Research and Practice to Improve Learning*, 59 (4), 96-103
- [76.] Ritz, R., Burris, S., &Brashears, T. (2013). The effects of a time management professional development seminar on stress and job satisfaction of beginning agriscience teachers in west Texas. *Journal of Agricultural Education*, 54(3), 1-14. doi: 10.5032/jae.2013.03001
- [77.] Riveros, A. M., & Tsai, T. S. T. (2011). Career commitment and organizational commitment in for-profit and non-profit sectors. *International Journal of Emerging Science*, 1(3), 324–340.
- [78.] Islam, T., Ali, G., & Ahmed, I. (2018). Protecting healthcare through organizational support to reduce turnover intention. *International Journal of Human Rights in Healthcare*, 11 (1), 4-12. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJHRH-03-2017-0012>
- [79.] Schraw, G., &Moshman, D. (1995). Metacognitive theories. *Educational Psychology*, 7(4), 351-371.
- [80.] Shashi, S. (2014). Teaching competency, professional commitment and job satisfaction-A study of primary school teachers. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education* 4(3), 44-64. Retrieved from www.iosrjournals.org
- [81.] Smith, J. M., & Mancy, R. (2018). Exploring the relationship between metacognitive and collaborative talk during group mathematical problem-solving—what do we mean by collaborative metacognition? *Research in Mathematics Education*, 20(1), 14–36. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14794802.2017.1410215>
- [82.] Smola, K. W., & Sutton, C. (2002). Generational differences: Revisiting generational work values for the new millennium. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 23, 363-382.
- [83.] Spencer, E., Lucas, B., & Claxton, G. (2012). Progression in creativity - developing new forms of assessment: A literature review. CCE, Newcastle.
- [84.] Srisrankulwong, K.L. (2005). Metacognitive regulation during elementary students' collaborative group work. *Interchange*, 49(2), 263–281. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10780-018-9327-4>
- [85.] Stadler, M., Scharrer, L., Macedo-Rouet, M., Rouet, J. F., &Bromme, R. (2016). Improving vocational students' consideration of source information when deciding about science controversies. *Reading and Writing*, 29(4), 705–729. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11145-016-9623-2>
- [86.] Stavrou, E. T., Kleanthous, T., &Anastasiou, T. (2016). Leadership personality and firm culture during hereditary transitions in family firms: Model development and empirical investigation. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 43(2), 187-206
- [87.] Steers, F. J. (2009). *The measurement of satisfaction in work and retirement*. Chicago: Rand McNally.
- [88.] Steinheider, B. (2016). Effects of sexual permissiveness on desirability of a partner as a function of low and high commitment to relationship. *Social Psychology Quarterly*, 55, 321–333
- [89.] Steinheider, B., Wuestewald, T., Boyatzis, R. E., &Krouter, P. (2012). 'In Search of a methodology of collaboration: Understanding research-practitioner philosophical differences in policing. *Police Practice and Research*, 13(4), 357-374.
- [90.] Sugiharto, Sorebima, T., Susilo,H., &Ibrohim,K. (2018). Role of nutraceuticals in gut health and growth performance of poultry. *J. Saudi Soc. Agric. Sci.* 15, 99-111.
- [91.] Tait, M. (2018). Linked references are available on JSTOR for this article: Resilience as a contributor to novice teacher success, commitment, and retention. *Teacher Education Quarterly*, 35 (4), 57-75.
- [92.] Takallou, F. (2011). The effect of metacognitive strategy instruction on EFL learners' reading comprehension performance and metacognitive awareness. *Asian EFL Journal*, 13(1), 272-300.
- [93.] Tonnessen, M., &Jefsen, R. (2009). Cognition and corporate governance: Understanding boards of

- directors as strategic decision-making groups. *Academy of Management Review*, 24(3), 489-505.
- [94.] Topolnytsky, G.L. (1998). Maintaining an internal market: Antecedents of willingness to change jobs. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 59(3), 425-453.
- [95.] Tweve, F. O. (2015). Is continuance commitment beneficial to organizations? Commitment performance relationship: a new look. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 15(5), 407-426.
- [96.] Valentine S., & Barnett T. (2013). Ethic code awareness, perceived ethical values, and organizational commitment. *J. Pers. Sell. Sales Manage*, 23, 359–367.
- [97.] Walker, W. D., Garton, B. L., & Kitchel, T. J. (2014). Job satisfaction and retention of secondary agriculture teachers. *Journal of Agricultural Education*, 45(2), 28-38.
- [98.] Wright, T.A., & Cropanzano, R. (2007). Shared influence and organizational behaviour: A meta analysis of situational variable expected to moderate participation outcome relationship. *Academy of Management Proceedings*, 364-37.
- [99.] Yang, Y. F. (2002). Reassessing readers' comprehension monitoring. *Reading in a Foreign Language*, 14, 18–42.
- [100.] Ylvisaker, M. (2005). Children with cognitive, behavioral, communication, and academic disability. In W. M. High, A. M. Sander, M. A. Struchen, & K. A. Hart (Eds.), *Rehabilitation interventions following traumatic brain injury: State of the science* (pp. 205-234). New York: Oxford University Press.
- [101.] Zhou, M., & Brown, D. (2017). Educational learning theories. *GALILEO Open*